

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-3, JUNE 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Representation of TIME in the Works of Graham Greene: A Study in Cognitive Metaphor

Dr. Tahmeena Hussain

Researcher,

Department of Linguistics,

University of Kashmir.

Prof (Dr) Musavir Ahmed

Head,

Department of Linguistics,

University of Kashmir.

Article History: Submitted-04/05/2025, Revised-14/06/2025, Accepted-17/06/2025, Published-30/06/2025.

Abstract:

This paper explores the representation of time in selected works of Graham Greene through the lens of Cognitive Metaphor Theory, a framework within Cognitive Linguistics developed by George Lakoff, Mark Johnson, Ron Langacker and Len Talmy. Cognitive Linguistics views language as a reflection of general cognitive processes and conceptual structures. Drawing on the theory of conceptual metaphors, the study investigates how time is metaphorically constructed in Greene's narratives, focusing on patterns such as "TIME AS MOTION" or "TIME AS A LOCATION". By analyzing novels like *The Power and the Glory*, *The End of the Affair* and *The Heart of the Matter*, the paper reveals how Greene's depiction of temporality reflects psychological, existential, and ethical dimensions, enriching our understanding of both his narrative technique and the cognitive underpinnings of temporal representation in literature.

Keywords: Cognitive Linguistics, Cognitive Metaphor, Source Domain, Target Domain and Conceptual Mapping.

Introduction

Writers frequently employ symbolic and metaphorical methods to represent time, which can be perceived, measured, and described in texts. Language offers a vast array of metaphorical and idiomatic expressions that convey time-related attributes. Time-oriented categorization encompasses two main aspects: sense of time, and its representation through signs and symbols. It also encompasses the selection of appropriate linguistic signs to accurately reflect the temporal dimension within a given element of actuality. The sense of time is primarily facilitated through language, although there are also pre-linguistic cognitive structures, such as gestalts and frames, that play a role in the formation of speech.

In literary texts, time is frequently depicted through various constructs, images, and comparisons. Kurt Vonnegut's prose often blends autobiographical elements with a collage-like style that fuses reality with fantasy, fiction with documentary facts, and logic with absurdity. In works such as *Slaughterhouse-Five* and *The Sirens of Titan*, Vonnegut's characters traverse different locations within a specific timeframe. In contrast, in *Timequake*, characters can exist in multiple time planes while remaining in a single location.

In Kurt Vonnegut's novel *The Sirens of Titan*, the time frameworks are depicted as a blend of reality and fantasy. This approach contributes to a sense of timelessness, making the demarcation of time and the sequential flow of events seem insignificant within the narrative. However, despite this overarching sense of timelessness, Vonnegut provides concrete time details, such as precise dates and the description of a spring afternoon in the northern hemisphere, which anchors the reader in the story's plausibility. Moreover, he includes detailed descriptions of how time is measured on Mars, such as the division of the year on Mars into 21 months with specific names

and the length of a Martian year compared to Earth's. These details lend a sense of authenticity to the narrative.

In *Timequake*, a term coined by Vonnegut, the author explores various time alterations. The novel, centred on the character Kilgore Trout, a science fiction writer, weaves together two main storylines. In 2001, Trout is a celebrated writer attending a conference, while in 2010, he is portrayed as destitute. Although the events in the novel do not follow a chronological order, each text begins with a distinct point of reference. The narrative begins in 1996, from the author's perspective: events and individuals from his early adulthood serve as emotional and ethical benchmarks for him during the summer of 1996. The year 2001 saw an abrupt temporal transition, causing time to compress and revert to 1991, repeating the events up to 2001. Subsequently, the author portrays 2010, shifting the tenses from past to present and illustrating the fluid nature of time in the novel.

Having entered eighty-eight—or ninety-eight, if the 'rerun' is considered—Kurt Vonnegut illustrates a quintessential feature of his writing: a disordered temporal structure. Readers are challenged to piece together a chronological framework of his narratives. In the prologue of *Timequake*, Vonnegut confesses to the randomness of these temporal shifts. He imagines himself alive in 2010, oscillating between 1996, where he truly exists, and a rerun instigated by a time quake, without clear delineation between these realities. This narrative structure resembles a cinematic experience, with the storyline rewinding and characters returning to their previous states a decade prior. For example, Zolton returns to his paraplegic state in the wheelchair, pressing the doorbell once more, while Monica resumes her work on Xanadu's financial plan when the time quake hits.

This abrupt alteration of existential coordinates is also a key narrative device in *Slaughterhouse-Five*. The protagonist, Billy Pilgrim, is concurrently present in Germany during World War II and the planet Tralfamadore, where he uncovers the profound nature of time: ‘... everything that ever has been always will be, and everything that ever will be always has been.’ A similar idea is expressed by a character in *The Sirens of Titan*: ‘Whatever we’ve said, friends, we’re saying still – such as it was, such as it is, such as it will be.’ This theme recurs throughout Vonnegut's works over several years.

Vonnegut does not confine his stories within strict temporal or spatial boundaries. His novels traverse various eras, such as the Second World War, 2016, the distant future, and the latter half of the 20th century, spanning the confines of and beyond the Solar System. Characters in his works effortlessly journey from Earth to Mars, Mercury, Titan, and Tralfamadore through dreams, radio waves, or UFOs. Portions of their lives may repeat, granting them the opportunity to relive a decade of their existence, as depicted in *Timequake*. This narrative style is marked by fragmented discourse, a random composition, along with the convergence of various temporal planes, time compressions, and ellipses.

In postmodern literature, texts are often depicted as a compilation of other texts, with time portrayed as a construct shaped by individual perception. Authors in this genre emphasize the personal experience of time, offering diverse portrayals of temporal experiences. This literary movement frequently employs a technique known as ‘narrative chaos.’ Authors disrupt the linear flow of the narrative by introducing character reminiscences or forward-looking events. In *Baudolino*, U. Eco continuously hints at future events for various characters. This method generates intrigue, internal tension, and a sense of unpredictability.

Similarly, Toni Morrison's *Jazz* is rich with flashbacks and lyrical digressions. The protagonist, Violet, attempts to piece together the story of Dorcas, a deceased girl who was her husband's mistress. The narrative frequently moves from the present to the past, particularly to the girl's funeral, where Violet creates a disturbance. Despite being fifty, Violet is described as still attractive when she disrupts the funeral (Morrison). Throughout the novel, Violet tries to reconstruct the past to comprehend what attracted her husband to Dorcas. The dual temporal planes are highlighted through the use of both present and past time frames.

Principal Attributes of Objective Time and Time in the Text

Time has several key characteristics that take on diverse characteristics within a script. One primary property is its ability to sequence events with a continuous and unidirectional flow. Another characteristic is its variability and fluidity as it transitions from the past to the future. The flow of time can vary in speed, and modern experiments, such as those involving atomic clocks, have shown the non-uniformity of time's flow. Scientists also describe the cyclic nature of time, evident in natural cycles, historical cycles, and economic cycles like Kondratiev's waves. These cycles suggest a repetition of phenomena and processes, implying that events on Earth and in time will perpetually recur.

Another significant essence of time lies in its dual nature of objectiveness and subjectiveness. It is also psychological, existing within the realms of consciousness, perception, and emotion. When a person suffers from brain damage, consciousness disruption, or depersonalization, their perception of time can become distorted, making it feel either excessively slow or fast, commonly paired with a fleeting unreality in the situation. These themes of consciousness divergence and distorted time perception are often explored in modern literature. For instance, in the writings of Russian

postmodernist Victor Pelevin, characters experience temporal transitions correlated with changes in their consciousness.

In both consciousness and literary text, time takes on a complex structure that encompasses a broad spectrum of meanings and an expansive, often surreal, plane. The literary world is crafted as a sophisticated, multi-layered construct with a narrative framework and a storyline where the conventional attributes of time are altered. Within this realm, time is unstable, diverse, and reversible. It becomes multi-faceted and distinct, both looking to the past and to the future, reflecting an irregular and fluid nature. This interrelation between shifts in time and corresponding shifts in space aligns with Mikhail Bakhtin's theory of the chronotope, which presents time and space as a unified concept.

The 20th century witnessed the emergence of literary works that could be read starting from any page, novels that lacked traditional endings, and stories with beginnings that commenced at the resolution or featured alternative endings. An example is V. Nabokov's *The Circle*, which intriguingly starts with 'Secondly' and concludes with 'Firstly'.

Authors often manipulate the sequence of events in their novels, shifting them from the final point to the origin, bypassing intervals and phases, pausing, freezing, stretching, or compressing time. Events may vanish at the author's discretion, only to reappear later. In Umberto Eco's *Foucault's Pendulum*, a narrator creates a text on a computer, subsequently deleting it, expressing the desire for it never to have happened. Although the text disappears, it can be restored with a simple keystroke.

J. Updike's *The Centaur* exemplifies the intertwining of reality and fantasy, mythology and autobiography, where the author employs innovative storytelling techniques, including mythological allusions, shifts between different literary worlds, reminiscences, internal

monologues, and polyphonic narration. The novel initially challenges readers to discern the timeline of the action—whether it occurs in 1947 or later—as the protagonist appears after an obituary has already been presented.

Russian author Dina Roubina, in her novel *On the Sunny Side of the Street*, reflects on the relationship between individuals and time, depicting time as ‘bottomless waters’ and ‘a shapeless substance’ that eludes grasp, likened to ‘shreds of fog’ that can be quantified and dissected but remain unfathomable and elusive.

Modern scholars have increasingly focused on the concept of the present moment. As Faulkner eloquently states, ‘It's all Now, you see. Yesterday will not be over until Tomorrow, and Tomorrow began ten thousand years ago’ (Faulkner). J.L. Borges similarly observes that the present always contains elements of both the past and the future. The character in Pelevin’s work proclaims, ‘I know for a long time already that the unique real instant of time is ‘now’’ (Borges). However, the notion of ‘now’ presents a paradox in physics, creating a conflict between the inevitability of cause and effect and continuous flux. (Sanfey).

The metaphor of the labyrinth serves as a powerful illustration of the existential concept of time. According to phenomenological perspectives, time is continuously being created without a definitive beginning or end. It is akin to an infinite line that lacks a successive nature, leaving us perpetually situated amid this temporal experience. In this labyrinth of mirror-like walls, each moment stands as a singular, playful signifier.

Postmodernist fiction writers have adeptly adopted this imagery of a temporal maze. For instance, the repeated scenes in the novels of Alain Robbe-Grillet generate a labyrinthine perception of time. On a different level, the use of metafiction—where a narrative exists within another narrative, each possessing its distinct pace of time—further constructs this labyrinth. These narratives embody the

myriad internal entrances, pathways, and exits characteristic of a temporal labyrinth. Within such a construct, the present moment is the sole conceivable reality, existing independently without an inherent connection to the past or future.

The following works by literary scholars and critics offer a comprehensive examination of the concept of time from a cognitive perspective, contributing to the understanding of how time and temporality are perceived and constructed in literature:

1. Peter Stockwell - *Cognitive Poetics: An Introduction*, provides an introduction to cognitive approaches to literature, discussing how narrative time and temporality are shaped by cognitive processes.
2. Reuven Tsur - *Toward a Theory of Cognitive Poetics*, delves into the cognitive mechanisms that influence our interpretation of poetic and literary texts, with a particular focus on the representation and perception of time.
3. David Herman – Works, such as *Storytelling and the Sciences of Mind* and *Basic Elements of Narrative*, explore the cognitive dimensions of narrative, including how readers construct and perceive time within literary contexts.
4. Lisa Zunshine - In *Why We Read Fiction: Theory of Mind and the Novel*, Zunshine examines the engagement of cognitive faculties, including temporal perception, with the narrative structures of fiction.
5. Alan Palmer - *Fictional Minds*, investigates how readers infer the mental states and temporal experiences of characters, affecting their understanding and interpretation of narrative time.
6. Monika Fludernik - *Towards a 'Natural' Narratology*, incorporates cognitive theories into narratology, focusing on how time is naturally perceived and structured within narrative forms.

7. Gérard Genette- *Narrative Discourse: An Essay in Method*, although not explicitly cognitive, offers a foundational analysis of narrative time that has greatly influenced the field of cognitive narratology.
8. Marie-Laure Ryan - *Narrative as Virtual Reality*, examines how immersive narrative experiences, including temporal elements, are constructed through cognitive engagement.

These references provide a rich and diverse foundation for exploring the cognitive aspects of time in literary studies, highlighting the interplay between narrative structures and cognitive perceptions.

Cognitive metaphor

Metaphor is a fundamental tool that enables us to understand abstract ideas and engage in complex reasoning. A wide range of topics, from everyday matters to intricate scientific theories, can only be grasped through the use of metaphor. Our metaphor system is central to our understanding of experience and to the way we act on that understanding.

A conceptual metaphor connects two semantic areas or domains; one domain is concrete (a thing, person, animal, object, direction, etc.), while the other is abstract (thought, emotion, notion, etc.). We refer to the second domain described metaphorically as the ‘target domain,’ and to the first domain that provides the metaphors as the ‘source domain.’ These two domains are linked together so that the ideas and knowledge from the source domain are ‘mapped’ onto the target domain by the conceptual metaphors. These mappings that inhere in the conceptual, rather than the linguistic system, are relatively stable in long term semantic memory and are invariably activated whether due to linguistic or non-linguistic processing.

The research in the field of metaphor analysis and its growing applicability in language and communication can be helpful in our understanding of how metaphors influence our general psychological and social thought process.

Conceptual Metaphors of Time in the Select Works of Greene

Time is an abstract idea, and we tend to understand it through the more concrete-seeming experience of space: time can flow, and it can stand still. Our past is better left behind because our future lies ahead. Graham Greene has depicted the target domain of time in a variety of source domains that are reflected in the conceptual metaphors of time given below:

1. [CM] TIME IS MOTION

(i) [LM/ME]: “When I closed the book, they were covered at once by the drift of time.” (Greene 143)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “Time flies when the rains are over,…” (Greene 210)

(iii) [LM/ME]: “Time passed very slowly; even the smoke of the shot seemed to remain in the air for an unnatural period.” (Greene 71)

(iv) [LM/ME]: “...how much time had passed since he had met the beggar in the plaza?” (Greene 127)

(v) [LM/ME]: “The darkness was always the same, and there were no clocks -there was nothing to indicate time passing.” (Greene 131)

(vi) [LM/ME]: “I mean the real future - the future that goes on.” (Greene 216)

(vii) [LM/ME]: “They fell silent and time passed, the shadow of the customs house shifted a few inches farther towards the river: the vulture moved a little, like the black hand of a clock.”(Greene3)

2. [CM] TIME AS A MOVING OBJECT

(i) [LM/ME]: “Time flies when the rains are over,..” (Greene 210)

3. [CM] TIME IS MOTION OF OBJECTS (ALONG A PATH)

(i) [LM/ME]: “St. Augustine asked where time came from. He said it came out of the future which didn’t exist yet, into the present that had no duration, and went into the past which had ceased to exist. I don’t know that we can understand time any better than a child” (Greene 149,150)

4. [CM] DURATION IS LENGTH

(i) [LM/ME]: “Ten years is a long time.” (Greene 184)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “Does the pain go on –a long time?” (Greene 205)

(iii) [LM/ME]: “... you’d have taken the wrong path a long time ago.” (Greene 86)

(iv) [LM/ME]: “He lit a candle and stuck it in its own wax on the dais: then sat down and waited: the man was a long time” (Greene 87)

(v) [LM/ME]: “It’s a long time.” (Greene 108)

(vi) [LM/ME]: “But that can take a long time” (Greene 181)

(vii) [LM/ME]: “Nobody really knew how long a second of pain could be.” (Greene 131)

5. [CM] TIME IS A LIMITED RESOURCE

(i) [LM/ME]: “...he couldn’t waste time looking any more” (Greene 95)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “He felt it was expected of him, though he couldn’t help thinking it was a waste of time.” (Greene 161)

(iii) [LM/ME]: “Don’t waste time. Hurry. When did you last...” (Greene 40)

(iv) [LM/ME]: “When he had finished, he lifted up the body and carried it back into the hut like a piece of furniture –it seemed a waste of time to have taken it out, like a chair you carry out into the garden and back again because the grass is wet.” (Greene 150)

6. [CM] TIME AS A STARTING POINT / DESTINATION

(i) [LM/ME]: “It comes suddenly on one in a screeching brake or a whistle in the air, the knowledge that time moves and comes to an end.” (Greene 131)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “She stood there in her black trousers, among the frozen puddles, and I thought, this is where a whole long future may begin.” (Greene 132)

(iii) [LM/ME]: “Life began five years ago.” (Greene 19)

7. [CM] TIME AS A BOUNDED SPACE

(i) [LM/ME]: “Her candour made allowances for nobody: the future, full of compromises, anxieties, and shame, lay outside.” (Greene 31)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “...I would badger her and badger her, as though I wanted to bring the future in now at the door, an unwanted and premature guest.” (Greene 44)

8. [CM] TIME AS AN EXTENSION

(i) [LM/ME]: “What was the time? How many hours of light had there been? It was impossible to tell.” (Greene 139)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “It was as though all the men in the past and all the men in the future cast their shade over the present.” (Greene 35)

(iii) [LM/ME]: “The long summer afternoon of twenty years ago stretched out its shadows towards me,…” (Greene 143)

9. [CM] TIME AS A LOCATION

(i) [LM/ME]: “In the future- that was where the sadness lay”. (Greene 149)

10. [CM] TIME IS A CONTAINER

(i) [LM/ME]: “St. Augustine asked where time came from. He said it came out of the future which didn’t exist yet, into the present that had no duration, and went into the past which had ceased to exist. I don’t know what we can understand time any better than a child.” (Greene 149,150)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “I wanted to warn him of the empty future, but instead I took another glass and said, I can’t stay long.” (Greene 123)

(iii) [LM/ME]: “It needs a God outside time to remember when everything changes.” (Greene 119)

11. [CM] TIME IS MONEY

(i) [LM/ME]: “These things take time to fix.” (Greene 47)

12. [CM] TIME AS A DESTINATION

(i)[LM/ME]: “He had come to the very edge of time: soon there would be no tomorrow and no yesterday, just existence going on forever.” (Greene 183)

13. [CM] TIME IS PURSUER

(i)[LM/ME]: “It’s a filthy night, ‘I said accusingly, and Henry added with apparent anxiety, ‘You’re wet through, Sarah. One day you’ll catch your death of cold.’” (Greene 11)

14. [CM] TIME IS AN ADVERSARY

(i)[LM/ME]: “He had the appearance of a businessman who had fallen on hard times.” (Greene 105)

15. [CM] TIME AS A BOUNDED SPACE

(i) [LM/ME]: “There is always one moment in childhood when the door opens and lets the future in”. (Greene 6)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “Her candour made allowances for nobody: the future, full of compromises, anxieties, and shame, lay outside.” (Greene 31)

(iii) [LM/ME]: “,..I would badger her and badger her, as though I wanted to bring the future in now at the door, an unwanted and premature guest.” (Greene 44)

16. [CM] TIME AS A CONTAINER

(i)[LM/ME]: “There is always one moment in childhood when the door opens and lets the future in.” (Greene 6)

17. [CM] TIME IS A CHANGER

(i) [LM/ME]: “He had nearly reached the state of permanency too, but he carried about with him still the scars of time - the damaged shoes implied a different past, the lines of his face suggested hopes and fears of the future.” (Greene 38)

18. [CM] TIME IS A LIVING ENTITY

(i)[LM/ME]: “...her face reddened when she cried - she looked ten years older, a middle-aged and abandoned woman - it was like the terrible breath of the future on his cheek.” (Greene 48)

19. [CM] TIME IS A CHANGER

(i)[LM/ME]: “He had nearly reached the state of permanency too, but he carried about with him still the scars of time - the damaged shoes implied a different past, the lines of his face suggested hopes and fears of the future.” (Greene 38)

20. [CM] TIME AS A DESTINATION

(i) [LM/ME]: “It comes suddenly on one in a screeching brake or a whistle in the air, the knowledge that time moves and comes to an end.” (Greene 131)

(ii) [LM/ME]: “She stood there in her black trousers, among the frozen puddles, and I thought, this is where a whole long future may begin.” (Greene 132)

21. [CM] TIME AS A LOCATION

(i) [LM/ME]: “In the future- that was where the sadness lay.” (Greene 149)

22. [CM] TIME IS A MOVING ENTITY

(i)[LM/ME]: “He felt like someone who has missed happiness by seconds at an appointed place.” (Greene 209)

Conclusion

This study attempts to draw a correlation between the various conceptual metaphors of TIME and the linguistic metaphors or metaphorical expressions from the select works of Greene, viz. *The Power and the Glory*, *The Heart of the Matter*, and *The End of the Affair*.

The total number of conceptual metaphors identified =22

The total number of linguistic metaphors identified = 39.

The conceptual domain of time is often understood through a spatial metaphor. It connects time and space using spatial reasoning. In this metaphor, time is like a river—constantly moving forward and carrying subtle nuances of cross-domain mappings. This way of understanding time plays a significant role in the study of cognitive linguistics. In the context of this qualitative research, conceptual metaphors serve as an overarching framework that encompasses and informs various literary devices such as themes, imagery, analogy, simile, and symbolism. It takes in its stride every subtle nuance from personification to the dream metaphor. It is a broader perspective wherein the meanings are not limited to dictionary usage. The reader thinks out of the box, as the language aspect is replaced by the thought process. Analyzing Greene's works in cognitive perspective, the readers thought extends beyond the boundaries of the literary language.

Works Cited:

Borges, Jorge Luis. "The Other." *The Atlantic*, 1967.

Borges, Jorge Luis. *Labyrinths: Selected Stories & Other Writings*. New Directions Publishing Corporation, 1986.

Brink, André. *States of Emergency*. Faber and Faber, 1988.

Doctorow, E. L. *The Book of Daniel*. Random House, 1971.

Eco, Umberto. *Baudolino*. Harvill Secker, 2002.

Eco, Umberto. *Foucault's Pendulum*. Random House, 2014.

Evans, Vyvyan. *Language and Time: A Cognitive Linguistics Approach*. Cambridge UP, 2013.

Faulkner, William. *Intruder in the Dust*. Vintage, 2015.

Fludernik, Monika. *Towards a "Natural" Narratology*. Routledge, 2002.

Genette, Gérard. *Narrative Discourse: An Essay in Method*. Translated by Jane E. Lewin, Cornell UP, 1993.

Greene, Graham. *The Power and the Glory*. Vintage, 2002.

Greene, Graham. *The End of the Affair*. Vintage, 2004.

Greene, Graham. *The Heart of the Matter*. Vintage, 2004.

Herman, David. *Storytelling and the Sciences of Mind*. MIT Press, 2017.

Lakoff, George. "The Contemporary Theory of Metaphor." *Metaphor and Thought*, edited by Andrew Ortony, 2nd ed., Cambridge UP, 1993.

Morrison, Toni. *Jazz*. Vintage, 2007.

Nabokova, Vera. "The Circle." *The New Yorker Magazine*, 1971.

Pelevin, Victor. *Buddha's Little Finger*. Penguin, 2001.

Pelevin, Victor. *Omon Ra* [Povest']. Eksmo, 2015.

Richards, I. A. *The Philosophy of Rhetoric*. Oxford UP, 1936.

Ryan, Marie-Laure. *Narrative as Virtual Reality*. Johns Hopkins UP, 2001.

Sanfey, James J. "Reality and Those Who Perceive It." *The Nature of Time: Geometry, Physics and Perception*, edited by R. Buccheri et al., Kluwer Academic Press, 2003.

Stockwell, Peter. *Cognitive Poetics: An Introduction*. Routledge, 2020.

Robbe-Grillet, Alain. *In the Labyrinth*. Calder Publications Limited, 2017.

Trout, Kilgore. *Venus on the Half-Shell*. Dell, 1982.

Tsur, Reuven. *Toward a Theory of Cognitive Poetics*. Sussex Academic Press, 2008.

Updike, John. *The Centaur*. Fawcett, 1964.

Vonnegut, Kurt. *Slaughterhouse-Five*. W. Ross Macdonald School Resource Services Library, 1969.

Vonnegut, Kurt. *The Sirens of Titan*. Gollancz, 2004.

Vonnegut, Kurt. *Timequake*. Vintage, 2019.

Zunshine, Lisa. *Why We Read Fiction: Theory of Mind and the Novel*. Ohio State UP, 2006.